

Oxo-Vanadium (IV) Chelates

A. Syamal

In continuation of our previous work¹⁻³ the syntheses of some oxo-vanadium(IV) complexes is reported in this short communication.

Vanady Isulphate reacts with benzoylacetanilide⁶ or substituted benzoylacetanilides (LH) around pH 4.5 to furnish green to bluish green complexes of the type (VOL_n). The oxo-vanadium(IV) complexes of benzoylacetanilides exhibit normal paramagnetic behaviour ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.7-1.8$ B.M.) responding to the requirement of one unpaired electron in the 3d¹ system. These complexes are less stable than the corresponding vanadyl acetylacetonates and do not form easily the hexa-coordinated adducts with co-ordinating solvents. The complexes are non-electrolytes.

Dimedone(LH) reacts with vanadylsulphate to produce green paramagnetic (1.74 B.M.) complex (VOL₂).

Salicylanilide (LH) reacts with vanadyl ion providing sky-blue complex (VOL₂). This is as usual paramagnetic. Substituted salicylanilides behave in a comparable manner.

A few of the representative complexes are listed in the Table.

TABLE I
Analysis and physical properties of oxo-vanadium(IV) complexes

Compound	Analytical Results		Colour	Magnetic Moment B.M. T _{emp} =305°K)
	%V	%N		
<i>bis</i> -Benzoylacetanilido-oxo-vanadium (IV) [VO (C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₂ N) ₂]	Found: 9.50 Reqd: 9.39	5.32 5.15	Light green	1.81
<i>bis</i> -Benzoyl-meta-nitroacetanilido-oxo-vanadium (IV) [VO (C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂) ₂]	Found: 8.10 Reqd: 8.05	8.92 8.84	Deep green	1.79
<i>bis</i> -Salicylanilido-oxo-vanadium (IV) [VO (C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂ N) ₂]	Found: 10.52 Reqd: 10.38	5.63 5.70	Sky blue	1.73
<i>bis</i> -Dimedonato-oxo-vanadium (IV) [VO (C ₈ H ₁₁ O ₄) ₂]	Found: 14.54 Reqd: 14.78	— —	Green	1.74

1. Dutta, Syamal and Ghosh, *this Journal*, 1966, 43, 526.
2. Dutta and Syamal, *ibid*, 1967, 44, 381
3. Syamal, D. Phil. Thesis, Burdwan University, 1966.
4. Syamal and Dutta, *this Journal*, 1967, 44, (accepted for publication); *Ind. J. Chem.*, (Under publication).
5. Dutta, Sengupta and Syamal, Unpublished studies.
6. Kibler and Weissberger, *Organic Synthesis* (Edited by E. C. Horning, John Wiley & Sons. Inc., New York), Coll. Vol-III, 1955, p-108.

Studies on the diffuse reflectance spectra and infra-red spectra of these complexes are in progress. The chelating properties of these ligands are being extended to other transition metals. Details will be published in due course.

Sincere thanks are due to Dr. R. L. Dutta and Prof. S. K. Siddhanta for keen interest and encouragement.

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
THE UNIVERSITY OF BURDWAN,
WEST BENGAL, INDIA.

Received, June 8, 1967.